

Queue Wait Time Prediction in Supercomputers

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I. INTRODUCTION

High-performance computing (HPC) systems are critical in advancing scientific research. They use schedulers for allocating resources to queued jobs [1]. Waiting time can vary, even among similar jobs, making it difficult to accurately estimate the exact time a job will wait in the queue. For users, knowing how long a job will wait is beneficial for adequate planning and avoiding frustration. Efficient job wait time estimation is also crucial for optimizing resource allocation.

This paper investigates the impact of job characteristics such as job size, wall time, and user behaviors on job wait time on leadership-class HPC systems. The paper evaluates the performance of different supervised learning algorithms for job wait time estimation. While this study focuses on a particular supercomputer, the processes and tools developed can be applied to any other leadership-class machine.

II. PROBLEMS/MOTIVATION

Modern space-sharing systems use resource-management and scheduling software such as PBS, SLURM, and Loadleveler to map jobs to available resources [2] [3]. These tools, however, do not provide users with any estimation of job wait time at the time of job submission. Policies such as first come first serve, longest job first, shortest job first or job scoring strategies are usually relied upon by HPC systems for scheduling users' jobs. However, additional policies are enforced to ensure that nodes are allocated to users fairly and do not lie idle. This makes job scheduling processes even more complicated and less transparent. For instance, backfilling prioritizes smaller jobs down the queue, enabling them to fill up small numbers of available nodes, thereby introducing additional uncertainty when predicting wait time [4].

The motivation for this study, therefore, is to evaluate the performance of different supervised learning algorithms, including Random Forest (RF), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), for predicting job wait times on HPC systems. We explore two formulations: regression to estimate the time a newly submitted job will wait in the queue and classification to label a job with a wait time range. We investigate the relationships between wait time and

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other job characteristics such as the number of nodes, wall time requested, and the queue to which the job is submitted.

III. APPROACH

We used the job log from Theta, a Cray XC40 machine, which consists of 496,537 jobs from August 2017 to December 2022. We started by analysing the job characteristics and user behaviors on the machine and how these characteristics correlate with job wait time. Figure 1a shows the distribution of the jobs submitted during the 5.5-year period. While the number of jobs served continuously decreased between 2018 and 2022, the job sizes and median job queue wait times increased over the years.

Figure 1b shows the distributions of wait times of jobs on different queues. We observed that jobs that requested more

(a) Theta served a large amount of jobs each year.

(b) Wait time varies significantly across different queues.

Fig. 1: Job characteristics on Theta over 5.5-year period

nodes spent more time in the queue than smaller jobs, as per Figure 2a. This may be because it is easier to find spaces to slot in smaller jobs. Also, it can be seen from Figure 2b that jobs with unusually long wall time spent less time in the queue compared to those with shorter wall time. These jobs could be mission-critical scientific applications that are accorded high priority on a case-by-case basis.

A. Data pre-processing

After analyzing the data, we preprocessed it. We removed outliers, specifically jobs in the top 5% or lowest 5% of queue time. Since the job logs contained many features for each job, we also reduced the dimensionality of the input with principal component analysis (PCA).

(a) Large jobs spent more time on the queue.

(b) Jobs with unusually long wall time waited less.

Fig. 2: Relationships between job size, wall time and wait time

B. Queue Wait time prediction

The large variation in wait times for jobs with similar characteristics makes predicting the wait time challenging. Most users, however, are more interested in knowing a time range in which they can expect to see their job start rather than the exact wait time. We compared multiple ML algorithms (RF, XGB, and MLP) for predicting a job’s wait time or the range of wait times. The major trade-offs between the learning algorithms are their speed and accuracy. Both RF and XGB are tree-based algorithms that solve ML problems in a fast, flexible and accurate manner. While XGB is an optimised gradient boosting algorithm that uses parallel tree boosting methodology, RF is based on bagging and uses multiple decision trees for predictions. Increasing the number of trees in a tree-based algorithm can help to improve the model performance but can increase the learning time of the model. Likewise, increasing the depth of each tree can capture more complex interactions but also pose the risk of over-fitting. Therefore it is crucial to find the trade-off for each dataset.

IV. RESULTS

A. Performance metrics

To evaluate the models, we use the error metrics Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Root-mean-square Error (RMSE), R^2 score, and accuracy, as well as the performance metrics learning time and prediction time, as proposed by [5]. The *learning time* is the time it takes to process all the historical data and build a model. Although the model learning phase would only be redone periodically to maintain reliable predictions, the learning time should be reasonable. The *prediction time* is the time it takes to apply the model to a new job. Fast predictions would be ideal in order to return the estimate to the user soon after the job has been submitted.

B. Results of regression analysis

Table I presents the performance of the tree-based models. The most accurate model in terms of MAPE was RF with a tree depth of 500. The error remained steady through a depth of 700. However, XGB has faster learning and prediction time than RF. At a tree depth of 500, it took only 51.4 seconds to train the XGB model on a single GPU node on Polaris and 0.16 seconds for the model to make a prediction, whereas it took approximately 12 minutes and 3.18 seconds, respectively, for RF to train and make predictions at the same tree depth.

Tree depth	10		20		50		100		300		500	
R^2	0.88	0.25	0.89	0.78	0.89	0.86	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89
RMSE	0.15	0.24	0.14	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14
MAPE	86	82	77	74	57	47	56	41	33	42	22	42
Learning time (sec)	14.5	1.8	30.07	2.76	73.0	9.63	150	17.9	446	36.6	750	51.4
prediction time (sec)	0.12	0.14	0.130.15	0.31	0.15	0.63	0.16	1.8	0.15	3.18	0.16	

TABLE I: Performance of regression models at different tree depths. Red RF, blue XGB

C. Results of classification analysis

The performance of the classification algorithms was measured in terms of their accuracy, the percentage of jobs with a correctly predicted wait time range. Figure 3 shows the *learning time* of RF and XGB at different tree depths, and Figure 4 shows the accuracy of both models evaluated on the test dataset. XGB had the best accuracy at each tree depth but had longer learning time than RF. At a tree depth of 10, XGB had an accuracy of 98% after learning for 6.9 seconds, outperforming RF, which had an accuracy of 86% after learning for 2.74 seconds. Finally we compared using an MLP and showed that the tree-based models outperformed MLP. We evaluated different numbers of hidden layers (n) and learning rates (lr) for the MLP classifier and n=6 and lr=0.1 showed the best performance. The best MLP had an accuracy of 71% on the test dataset.

Fig. 3: Learning time of XGB and RF classification models at different tree depths

Fig. 4: Accuracy of predicted wait times by XGB and RF classification models at different tree depths

V. CONCLUSION

Job characteristics and user behaviors can impact queue wait time in HPC systems. Supervised ML algorithms can effectively predict job queue wait times. XGB and RF showed better performance for the wait time prediction task compared to MLP, when evaluated on historical data from the Theta Cray XC40 machine.

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